

THE DEFINED BENEFIT PENSION SCHEME AND RETIREES' FINANCIAL SECURITY: A STUDY OF THE UNIFIED LOCAL GOVERNMENT RETIREES, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

Umoh, Emem Umoh
Department of Sociology and Anthropology
Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Uyo, Uyo

Abstract

This study examined retirees' financial security and the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) among the unified local government retirees in Akwa Ibom. The major objectives of the study were to examine the impact of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme on the monthly expenditure and emergency needs of the unified local government retirees in Akwa Ibom State. A survey research design was adopted by the researcher for the study. Fair Allocation Theory served as a framework. Study respondents were randomly selected among the targeted population of retirees who retired between 1980 and 2020 and are collecting their pension. A sample size of 546 study respondents was drawn by simple random sampling method to represent all 31 local government areas of Akwa Ibom State. Data were collected through the Pension and Retirees' Welfare Assessment Tool (PARWAT). Data collected were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r). The findings of the study revealed that the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure (MTE) of the unified local government retirees in Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant ($r = 0.874, p < 0.001$) which indicate that the pension paid determine the monthly expenditure of the retirees. The Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees (EMN) of Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant at $r = 0.876, p < 0.001$. This indicated that the pension paid to the retirees determine their level and kinds of responses to their emergency needs. It was discovered that the paid pension under the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) is not enough to give the retirees a sustainable welfare. The researcher recommended among others that the state government should harmonize pension in accordance to inflation to ensure financial security of the retirees.

Keywords: Defined Benefit Pension Scheme, Pension, Retirees and Financial Security

Introduction

The administration of pensions for retirees has remained a critical challenge, especially in the public sector, over the past several years. According to Yusuf (2022), the distribution of these benefits has been characterised by notable irregularities and inconsistencies. As a result, pension liabilities have surged to a level where the government has found it increasingly difficult to fulfil its commitments. This situation has led to considerable hardship, poverty, and unacceptable living conditions for many civil service pensioners. Numerous individuals have been forced to beg for their essential needs, and some have tragically died while waiting for their pension payments (Yusuf, 2022). The

management of pensions has emerged as a pressing issue for governments across developed and developing countries.

Yusuf (2022) further notes that several pension systems have been established across African nations, including Nigeria. Before implementing the Contributory Pension Act in 2004, Nigeria relied on a Defined Benefit Scheme (DBS) for its pension framework. Emola and Obasi (2011) indicate that the Defined Benefit System has become increasingly unsustainable, with national liabilities estimated at N2.3 trillion, posing a significant challenge for the Federal Government in managing this considerable financial obligation. The rise in pension entitlements has further intensified this issue, impeding the government's capacity to fulfil its pension obligations. This situation is further complicated by the mismanagement of pension funds by those tasked with their oversight, resulting in a decline in pensioners' financial well-being and underscoring the pension system's shortcomings.

The difficulties associated with pension management in Nigeria have raised concerns regarding the financial security of retirees. According to Stewart (2007), pension benefit security has re-emerged as a significant concern in both economic and political discussions across numerous nations, particularly in light of notable instances where pension benefits were lost due to the bankruptcy of plan sponsors, resulting in underfunded pension schemes. In response, certain countries have implemented stringent funding regulations to safeguard pension benefits, as exemplified by the approach adopted by the Dutch authorities.

The concept of retirement has undergone significant changes in its definition, as various scholars have approached it from diverse viewpoints. Oniye (2004) asserts that retirement signifies a separation from employment, accompanied by considerations for the future. Mojisola (2019) identifies factors such as deteriorating health, advancing age, or the completion of mandated service years as potential triggers for retirement. Maji (2014) notes that the Retirement Age Harmonization Act of 2012 establishes the retirement age for judicial officers and academic personnel in higher education at 65 and 70 years, respectively, reflecting the belief that "the older, the wiser." Regardless of the specific age at which one retires, all retirees are entitled to receive gratuity, pension, and other associated benefits. According to Amaike (2016), retired public servants typically receive compensation in the form of gratuity and pension. Consequently, the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme is designed to address the pension requirements of retirees, ensuring their welfare during retirement.

The Akwa Ibom State Unified Local Government Pension Board is tasked with the obligation of disbursing the Defined Benefit Pension (DBP), which represents the pension framework adopted by the state government for retirees of the Local Government Service. While the Federal Government of Nigeria has transitioned from defined benefit pension schemes to defined contributory pension schemes, the Akwa Ibom State Government continues to maintain the defined benefit pension schemes at the state and local government levels to ensure the welfare of its employees during retirement.

The challenge of inadequate funding in defined benefit pension schemes, as noted by Yusuf (2022), calls for a comprehensive assessment of the operational efficiency of these schemes, particularly concerning the financial security of retirees. Consequently, it is essential to evaluate the effectiveness of the defined benefit schemes to determine whether they have successfully provided financial security to the retirees of the Akwa Ibom State Unified Local Government Pension Board, which remains a priority for the Akwa Ibom State government.

Statement of the Problem

The Defined Benefit Pension Scheme is designed to ensure that retirees do not encounter financial hardships during their retirement years. It provides employees with a sense of financial stability by creating plans that guarantee a consistent income throughout their retirement (Fapohunda, 2013). The primary goal is to secure the financial well-being of workers by formulating strategies that can deliver dependable income upon their retirement (Fapohunda, 2013). However, the implementation and management of Defined Benefit Pension Schemes in Nigeria have been found lacking, resulting in heightened concerns among public servants as they near retirement. The reliability of pensions in Nigeria falls short of providing adequate financial security for retirees. Okafor (2001) highlighted the particularly harsh and degrading conditions experienced by many individuals who, after dedicating their most productive years to public service, are left to confront the uncertainties of life without sufficient retirement support, often receiving minimal attention from government officials at all levels.

The Defined Benefit Pension Scheme currently in operation shows discrepancies depending on the retirement tiers of public servants. A considerable number of pensioners are facing challenges in meeting the primary aim of retirement pensions, which is to provide a stable standard of living. Those retiring from lower positions, whose pension benefits fall short of ensuring their well-being, particularly struggle to achieve the essential objectives of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme, namely financial sustainability and security in their post-service lives, especially when compared to their higher-ranking counterparts. This quest for financial stability has compelled many retirees to explore alternative income sources to improve their chances of survival, particularly in the context of irregular pension disbursements by pension authorities (Umoh, 2024) and the prevailing economic instability.

The challenge facing the Defined Benefit Pension Schemes (DBPS) is the inability of the pension to provide financial security for retirees of the unified local government retirees in Akwa Ibom State, which is the identified gap this research work sought to fill. Against this backdrop, this research work sought to examine the capacity of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) to offer financial security to the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the capacity of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) to offer financial security to the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives of the study were to;

1. examine the capacity of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) to cover the monthly expenditure of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State
2. examine the capacity of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) to cater for emergency needs of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were considered for testing of the study variables;

1. H_0 = there is no significant relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State
2. H_0 = there is no significant relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme

(DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State

Literature Review

Pension and Monthly Expenditure

Luković and Savićević (2021) emphasize that Defined Benefit Pension schemes are facing considerable funding difficulties on a global scale, leading to pension-related challenges in various countries over the past few decades. Recently, there has been a surge in interest from policymakers around the world regarding pensions as a means to encourage privately funded retirement savings in light of an ageing workforce (World Bank Report, 2006). Pensions have become increasingly vital within the economic structures of nations due to the growing population of retirees and the ongoing financial obligations to these individuals, particularly concerning defined benefit pension schemes (Fapohunda, 2013). In Nigeria, civil servants across both public and private sectors view retirement as a significant issue (Garba and Mamman, 2014), largely because of the disconnect between pension benefits and escalating inflation, which has resulted in a heightened cost of living for retirees.

The Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) provides pension as a financial mechanism established to provide employees with a source of income during their retirement years aimed at taking care of the life expenditure of the retiree. According to Fapohunda (2013), a pension represents funds allocated by either the employer, the employee, or both, ensuring that employees have a financial resource to rely on upon retirement. This arrangement is designed to prevent financial hardship in old age. A pension plan is formulated in advance of the employee's service years to ensure a steady income stream throughout retirement. Its primary objective is to offer workers financial security by creating plans that guarantee income during retirement or for their beneficiaries in the event of their death. The rationale behind pension schemes is twofold: firstly, organizations have a moral responsibility to provide a reasonable level of social security for their employees, particularly those who have dedicated many years of service. Secondly, these schemes reflect the organization's commitment to the welfare of its employees. Typically, the pension amount is calculated based on a percentage of the employee's earnings, averaged over several years, and multiplied by the total years of service with the company.

According to Chukwuma and Pretoria (2018), pension systems, which provide financial support for retirement, old age, and survivors' benefits following death, represent a fundamental aspect of social security recognized by the International Labour Organization (ILO) through Convention No. 102. The ILO has been actively engaged in social security issues since its inception in 1919, with intensified efforts beginning in 1966. Nevertheless, the mechanisms for pension disbursement have encountered significant distortions, limitations, and challenges in numerous nations. These issues have been particularly pronounced in less developed countries, notably Nigeria until recent governmental initiatives have addressed these concerns (Chukwuma and Pretoria, 2018). The pension system in Nigeria is insufficient to serve as a sole source of income. Okafor (2001) noted that it is particularly inhumane and degrading for many individuals who, after dedicating their most productive years to public service, are abandoned to confront the uncertainties and challenges of life without adequate retirement benefits, often receiving little attention from government authorities at all levels.

Pension and Emergency Needs of Retirees

The World Bank (2004) characterizes a pension as a type of income that is provided to workers or their spouses following retirement, disability, or death. This income is typically disbursed regularly by the government or an organization to individuals who are officially recognized as retired after completing a designated period of service, generally ranging from a minimum of fifteen years to a maximum of thirty-five years. Supporting this definition, Fapohunda (2013) emphasizes that the purpose of a pension is to offer workers financial security by establishing plans that ensure a reliable income against emergencies upon retirement or for dependents in the event of death. Idowu (2006) further elaborates that pensions serve as a form of social security and welfare for elderly or retired individuals who are no longer engaged in active labour. It is important to note that the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) is a structured financial arrangement that outlines its organization and operation, aiming to provide peace of mind to workers, encourage productivity, and ensure the well-being of both pensioners and their dependents (Idowu, 2006).

One of the primary purposes of a pension is to provide a form of social security against emergency needs for employees, allowing them to focus on their work without the concern of how they will meet their future needs upon retirement (Umoh and Peters, 2023). This assurance serves as a significant motivator, contributing to lower employee turnover as individuals feel appreciated and driven to perform, which in turn fosters ethical conduct and enhances productivity (Egbuta, 2001; Fapohunda, 2013; Mohammed, 2013; Ali, 2014). Additionally, pensions encourage individuals who may not otherwise save to set aside funds for their future requirements against emergencies.

Fapohunda (2013) elaborated that a defined benefit pension scheme is a framework through which an employer offers a pension to employees upon their retirement or provides deferred benefits to those who exit the organization. This indicates that the system is intended to ensure that employees can maintain a good standard of living against emergency during retirement that is reasonably comparable to what they experienced while employed. Pension programs are typically established to safeguard the elderly and retirees from the risks associated with ageing, poverty, and other uncertainties. While the contributory pension scheme serves to foster a culture of savings among current employees which in this context, a pension represents a contractual agreement for a fixed amount to be disbursed regularly to a retiree by either a government entity or a private company after a designated period of employment (fifteen years, effective from June 2004) and when the individual is deemed too old to work or has reached the legal retirement age, the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) is shouldered by the employee to secure the lives of the retirees throughout their lifetime in retirement (Fapohunda, 2013).

Pension refers to a regular income received by retirees every month, which is allocated by the employer to support the employee's financial well-being during retirement against emergencies. As noted by Elekwa *et al.* (2011), a pension constitutes a recurring payment or annuity provided to an employee who qualifies for benefits based on age, earnings, and length of service. Adams (2005) describes a pension as the sum disbursed by a government or corporation to an employee after a designated period of employment, particularly when the individual is deemed too old or unwell to continue working or has reached the legally defined retirement age for financial protection against needs. According to Ozor (2006), a pension may also include a lump sum payment made to an employee upon their exit from active service, typically distributed in monthly instalments. These payments

can vary in nature, being either contributory or non-contributory, fixed or variable, and may be organized through group or individual plans, insured or trustee arrangements, and can be offered by private or public entities, as well as single or multiple employers. Pension represents a formal obligation within any employment context; it is both a legal and economic responsibility that employers are required to uphold in their contractual agreements with employees, as well as a demonstration of goodwill towards them to give them financial security to meet their life needs (Omoni, 2013).

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Fair Allocation

The theory of fair allocation as explained by Thompson (2011) addresses specific issues related to the distribution of resources. It introduces precise concepts aimed at assessing the treatment of individuals or groups about each other, including principles such as no-envy, egalitarian equivalence, and both individual and collective lower or upper limits on welfare. Additionally, it explores ideas surrounding equal or equivalent opportunities, along with various frameworks that expand upon these concepts.

The theory of fair allocation is frequently viewed in a positive light when compared to social choice theory, particularly in the context of finding alternatives to Arrow's impossibility theorem (Biswas *et al.*, 2023). This favourable perception is often linked to its more modest objectives in contrast to social choice theory, as it does not seek a comprehensive ranking of all options but instead focuses on a selection of "fair" alternatives. Additionally, its effectiveness is due to an expanded informational foundation (Biswas *et al.*, 2023).

This theory is adopted by the researcher to address the allocation of pension through the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) as it relates to the well-being of the unified local government retirees in Akwa Ibom State. The components of the fair allocation theory explain the need for fairness and equity in the allocation of resources. This explains the need for fair allocation of pensions to satisfy the monthly expenditure, emergency needs and other aspects of the well-being of the retirees.

Social Choice Theory

Social choice theory is an economic framework that examines the possibility of organizing a society in a manner that accurately represents the preferences of its individuals. This theory was formulated by economist Kenneth Arrow and was introduced in his 1951 publication, *Social Choice and Individual Values* (Sen, 2008). In the 20th century, Arrow expanded the theory of social choice to encompass more than just the examination of majority rule characteristics (Sen, 2008). His generalization of social choice theory inquires whether it is feasible to establish a rule that effectively combines individual preferences, evaluations, votes, and decisions while adhering to fundamental criteria for what constitutes an acceptable rule.

Arrow's social choice theory encompasses a wide range of individual preferences, extending beyond merely political selections, and examines various potential mechanisms for arriving at collective decisions, rather than being limited to a straightforward majority voting system. Organizing society in a manner that accommodates the diverse and numerous individual preferences presents significant challenges (Arrow, 1963). Arrow identified five essential criteria that must be satisfied for societal choices to accurately represent the preferences of its members. These criteria are as follows:

Universality: The decision-making process must produce a comprehensive ranking of all preferences and maintain consistency under identical circumstances.

Responsiveness: An increase in an individual's preference for a particular option should lead to an increase or, at the very least, no change in the overall social preference for that option, but it must never result in a decrease.

Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives: The addition or removal of certain options should not affect the relative ranking of other options.

Non-imposition: The aggregated social preferences must emerge from various combinations of individual preferences.

Non-dictatorship: The decision-making process must reflect the preferences of multiple individuals rather than being dominated by a single person. (Arrow, 1963)

Utilizing these criteria, Arrow formulated his Impossibility Theorem. This theorem posits that it is unattainable to arrange society in a way that mirrors individual preferences without contravening one of the five established conditions. Consequently, the selection of a social choice rule will invariably necessitate some form of compromise among Arrow's five axiomatic conditions.

In the application of the Social Choice theory to the study, it is imperative to explain the theory in the dimension that the increasing needs of retirees are facing a pension which may not be able to take care of all the emergency needs within a rising inflation economic regime. This scenario propels the retirees into considering what might be their monthly expenditures based on their position of choice to see how the paid pension can undertake the needs of the retirees. This decision of choice is based on preference and varies from one retiree to another. Through this social choice practice, retirees have been able to cope with their pension over the years in their retirement.

Methodology

The study examined the impacts of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DPBS) on the financial security of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State. Survey research method was adopted for this study because the research study covers a large population and a complex study population. Simple random sampling method was used for the purposes of selecting study participants. The study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State through Akwa Ibom State Local Government Pension Board. Retirees who retired from local government service between 1980 and 2020, who are depending on pension, as managed by the Akwa Ibom State Local Government Pension Board (AKSLGPB) were directly engaged as the study population. The Akwa Ibom State Local Government Pension Board is a board in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service Commission.

Since the population of the study area is a known population, the sample size for the study was calculated using Cochran's Formula to be 547. The researcher, through the Akwa Ibom State Local Government Pension Board 2024 screening exercise engaged the sample size of 547 for the study.

Simple random sampling technique was adopted by the researcher with her assistants for the selection of study participants. The sample size (547) was divided for the available retirees during the 2024 Pensioners Screening Exercise from the 31 local government areas based on the availability of retirees and willingness to participate in the study. The instrument used in this study was questionnaires titled "Pension and Retirees' Welfare Assessment Tool" (PARWAT) as developed by the researcher. The questionnaire

contained questions that assessed the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents as well as questions that required candid opinions of the respondents on the substantial matter. The questionnaire contained closed ended questions which sought to collect information on the opinions of the respondents.

Data collected from the field through the use of PARWAT questionnaire were analysed with Pearson Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Result

Hypotheses 1

H₀: there is no significant relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State

Pearson Product Moment Correlation through SPSS was used for testing hypothesis 1 which sought to establish whether there is a relationship between the the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure of the unified local government retirees (MTE) of Akwa Ibom State as presented in the table below.

Table 1: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between The Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the Monthly Expenditure (MTE) of the Unified Local Government Retirees of Akwa Ibom State

Correlation between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and Monthly Expenditure of the Unified Local Government Retirees (MTE (n =547)

		DBPS	MTE
DBPS	Pearson Correlation	1	.874**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	547	547
MTE	Pearson Correlation	.874**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	547	547

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 shows that the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (r) between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure (MTE) of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant ($r = 0.874, p < 0.001$). Hence, the null hypothesis of hypothesis one which states that there is no significant relationship between the the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure (MTE) of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State, was not supported. This implies that the alternate hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between the the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure (MTE) of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State is hereby accepted. This indicates that the Defined Benefit Pension does not garter for the monthly expenditure of the unified local government retirees in Akwa Ibom State. By extension, this implies that the Defined Benefit Pension Schemes lacks the financial value to give to the retirees of the Unified Local Government Board the expected buying capacity as expected by the retirees. The positive relationship between the study variables as captured in

Table 1 showing hypothesis 1, indicated by the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (r) which is +0.874. The rules state that there exists a high positive or negative correlation when $r = \pm 0.70$ to ± 0.90 . In the case of the correlation (r) between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State, the Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) = +0.874 which supports a high positive statistical significance between the two variables; the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State and its statistical significant is lower than 0.01 level of significant.

Hypotheses 2

H₀: there is no significant relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and Capacity to meet the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) was used for testing Hypotheses 2 which sought to establish whether there is a relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees (EMN) of Akwa Ibom State as presented in the table below;

Table 2: Showing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and Capacity to meet the Emergency Needs (EMN) of the Unified Local Government Retirees of Akwa Ibom State

Correlation between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and Emergency Needs of the Unified Local Government Retirees (EMN) (n =547)

		DBPS	EMN
DBPS	Pearson Correlation	1	.876**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	547	547
EMN	Pearson Correlation	.876**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	547	547

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (r) of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees (EMN) of Akwa Ibom State was highly positive and statistically significant at $r = 0.876$, $p < 0.001$. Hence, the null hypothesis of hypothesis two which stated that there is no significant relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees (EMN) of Akwa Ibom State was not supported and thereby rejected. This implies that the alternate hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees (EMN) of Akwa Ibom State was accepted. This shows that the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme does not provide pensioners with the financial capacity to make available resources to take care of the

emergency needs of the retirees. The implication here is that pension, as offered by the Defined Benefit Pension Schemes (DBPS), does not give retirees financial provisions for savings to take care of their emergencies. The high positive relationship between the study variables as captured in hypothesis two is indicated by the Pearson Product-moment Correlation (r) which is $+0.876$. The rules state that there exists a high positive or negative correlation when $r = \pm 0.70$ to ± 0.90 . In the case of the tested hypotheses which stated that there is no significant relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees (EMN) of Akwa Ibom State, the correlation (r) between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees (EMN) of Akwa Ibom State, $r = +0.875$ which supports a high positive statistically significant relationship between the two variables and the statistically significant is lower than 0.01 level of significant at 0.000. Therefore, the tested null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternate state is accepted which states that there is a significant relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees (EMN) of Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study show that for hypothesis one there exists a highly positive relationship between the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the monthly expenditure (MTE) of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State, it is and statistically significant at Pearson Product-moment Correlation $r = 0.874$, $p < 0.001$. This shows that the Unified Local Government Pension Board retirees depend on their pensions for their monthly expenditures. This has to cover their feeding, bills and social contributions which are necessary factors for the well-being of the retirees. Analysis of findings showed that most retirees of the unified local government areas of Akwa Ibom State do not agree with their pensions as a source of financial security with the capacity to take care of their monthly expenditures. This has revealed that most of the retirees agreed that their pension is not enough to guarantee their well-being.

Further analysis of gathered data through questionnaires shows that the Defined Benefit Pension Schemes lack harmonization that ought to bring about changes in payment values to correspond with changing economic situation in the Nigeria. The emergence from this is that the value of pension paid to the retirees through the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme is deteriorating by the day due to the rising level of inflation with corresponding monthly demands of the retirees for the sustainability of their well-being. These findings disagree with Fapohunda (2013) who posits that the primary goal of pension is to secure the financial well-being of workers by formulating strategies that can deliver dependable income upon their retirement.

The Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) does not offer the retirees of the Unified Local Government Board, Akwa Ibom State the financial resources to take care of their well-being in terms of meeting their emergency needs. This was ascertained by the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (r) of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) and the emergency needs of the unified local government retirees (EMN) in Akwa Ibom State that was highly positive and statistically significant at $r = 0.876$, $p < 0.001$. The findings shows that the pension as paid to the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State does not give them the savings power for emergencies. This analysis of data gathered revealed that the majority of the retirees thought that their pension is not enough to take care

of their monthly demands and pension does not remain for emergencies. By implications, this further showed that the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State do not have savings from their pension for any emergencies. The majority of respondents through questionnaires agreed they are in debt and they do not think of emergencies because of the poor value of the pension paid to them through the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme. These findings also disagree with Fapohunda (2013) on the position that pension provides employees with a sense of financial stability by creating plans that guarantee a consistent income throughout their retirement.

5. Conclusion

This research work sought to examine the roles of the Defined Benefit Pension Scheme (DBPS) in offering financial security to the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State. Data gathered through questionnaires from 546 study respondents and analysed with Person Product Moment Correlation through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) revealed that the pension paid to the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State lacks the capacity to take care of the monthly expenditure of the retirees and does not remain for savings by the retirees for their emergency needs. This position revealed that the lack of pension harmonization by the Akwa Ibom State Government has led to the poor value of the pension paid to the retirees as compared to the present rising inflation which is a key factor to the high cost of living. This has affected the well-being of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State.

6. Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the researcher based on the summary of findings and conclusion drawn from the study;

1. The Akwa Ibom State Government should engage in pension harmonization to improve the value of pension to meet the monthly expenditure of the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State.
2. The government should make available other social welfare packages like a special healthcare service package for the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State to make up for their emergency needs.
3. There should be a review of pensions paid through the Defined Benefit Pension Schemes to the unified local government retirees of Akwa Ibom State to improve pension scales for years and levels of retirement.

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